

**IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF USING OUTSIDE-
CURRICULAR LEARNING SOURCES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS'
ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS**

Rjabova Zarafshon Davronovna

Doctoral student at Samarkand State University

Abstract: This article describes the importance of improving students' speaking skills in a foreign language, the need for resources for independent use in extracurricular situations. It also provides important information about the importance of speaking skills, their formation in the native language, speech and its features. These serve as initial skills for conducting research.

Keywords: speech skills, foreign language, source, acquisition, speech, student, education, teacher, communicative approach, thinking.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching students to express their thoughts freely and correctly is very important for society, both psychologically and methodologically, and is one of the current issues. The concept envisages the development of the standard of skills and abilities required in each grade in the four main types of speech activity acquired through teaching the native language: listening and understanding speech, speaking, reading and writing, and the dynamics of acquiring the skills to communicate in the form of independently exchanging and expressing opinions in various speech situations that arise during study and work, in the family and in public places, perceiving the heard material, as well as obtaining information by reading written sources, and expressing one's attitude to events.

MAIN PART

Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on language tools (words, word combinations, sentences). Speech performs the function of communication and information, the function of expressing and influencing mutual thoughts with emotions. Well-developed speech serves as one of the important means of active human activity in society. For a student, speech is a tool for successful learning at school. For speech activity, as well as for developing the speech of primary school students, it is necessary to observe several conditions:

1. There must be a requirement for the emergence of human speech. The methodological requirement for developing students' speech is to create a situation in which the student expresses his/her opinion, the desire and need to express something orally or in writing,

2. Any speech must have content, material. The more complete, rich, valuable this material is, the more meaningful its statement will be.

3. Thought is understandable only if it is expressed using words, word combinations, sentences, and speech turns that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for the successful development of speech is to arm speech with language tools. There are a number of aspects of mastering speech. These are:

1. Mastering the norms of the literary language.

2. Mastering important speech skills necessary for every member of our society, namely reading and writing skills.

3. Improving the speech culture of primary school students. In the development of speech, three areas are clearly distinguished: 1) work on words; 2) work on word combinations and sentences; 3) work on coherent speech. Lexicology (together with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, syntax serve as the linguistic basis for working on words, word combinations and sentences; coherent speech is based on logic, literary studies and the linguistics of complex syntactic wholes.

Professor S. Matchonov emphasizes that a number of clearly defined requirements must be observed in developing the speech of primary school students:

1. The students' speech should be meaningful.
2. There should be logic in the speech.
3. The speech should be clear.
4. The speech should be rich in language means.
5. The speech should be understandable.
6. The speech should be expressive.
7. The speech should be correct.
8. The speech should be cultured.

Speech is an important tool in developing students' thinking, especially in younger students. Speech is not only a means of expressing thought, but also a tool for its formation. A.N. Leontiev describes the process of speech development as follows: “The process of speech development and growth is not a quantitative change, but a qualitative change, expressed in the increase in the child's vocabulary and the associative connection of words, since it is a real developmental process that encompasses all the functions, aspects and connections of speech, being internally connected with the development of thinking and consciousness.”

K.D. Ushinsky, justifying the need to teach children in their native language and developing a methodology for the initial teaching of children's native language, expresses his views on the philosophical, self-development, and educational

Jaborov S.S. Psychological foundations of thinking and speech. – M-T.: Labirint-Illm-fan, 2019.

characteristics and laws of children's language acquisition, the relationship between language and thinking. In Russian science, research on the ontogenesis of

speech was carried out based on the cultural-historical theory of L.S. Vygotsky and the activity theory of A.N. Leontiev. As a result, a system of views was formed that the emergence and development of children's speech occurs in the processes of their communication with the people around them. As a result, a system of views was formed that the emergence and development of children's speech occurs in the processes of their communication with people around them. Based on the principles of L.S. Vygotsky and A.N. Leontiev, A.A. Leontiev developed the concept of the

formation of speech activity, which he considered as the main type of activity.

He notes that the development of a child's speech is, first of all, the development of communication methods, the mastery of which requires the formation of language skills. The most important stages of speech acquisition fall on preschool age. Based on this, special attention is currently being paid to the study of certain stages in the development of speech. Scientists have realized that the pre-speech stage plays an important role and are analyzing it in detail.

K.D. Ushinsky noted that "... a child can easily and quickly learn so much in two to three years that even if he diligently studies for twenty years, he will not be able to master half of it."

Although scientific research has been conducted on the issue of teaching a foreign language in general secondary education, scientific research work related to the methodology of the communicative approach in teaching English in general secondary education, where education is organized in the Uzbek language, is required. In the article, the following tasks were performed in order to improve the methodology of teaching English to schoolchildren based on the communicative approach:

-Analysis of the concepts of teaching a foreign language in general secondary education, didactic, psycholinguistic, methodological and pedagogical principles, theories of foreign language acquisition and foreign language learning;

-Analysis of the content of English language teaching (speech topics, skills and language material);

-determine the level of interlingual interference in teaching English at the A1 level, use innovative pedagogical technologies to prevent errors, ensure communication and interaction in classes;

¹ Williams M., Burden R. L. Psychology for language Teachers. A social constructivist approach. – L.: Cambridge University Press, 2010. – P. 40.

-organize and conduct experimental work on teaching English as a means of communication and interaction, and develop methodological recommendations based on the results of the research.

In clarifying the essence of the principles of the methodology, work was carried out based on psychological and linguistic laws and regulations, and the following psycholinguistic principles were summarized:

1. Increase students' motivation (internal motivation) to learn and master a foreign language.
2. Encourage students' age-appropriate physical activity during classes.
3. Make students aware of the similarities between their native language and the foreign language being studied.
4. Develop students' intermediate language (metalanguage) experiences.
5. Teach students to use the connection between their native language and the foreign language being studied.
6. Introduce students to the structure of the foreign language being studied.
7. Individual approach, that is, conduct psycho-pedagogical activities taking into account the characteristics of each student (the nature of each student, what they are capable of, their interests, who they make friends with, what they have a negative attitude towards).

CONCLUSION

The pedagogical principles of teaching foreign languages in general secondary education are described in detail in scientific sources in Uzbek and Russian as didactic principles. However, in foreign literature, the pedagogical principle is studied separately. In addition, resources for improving speaking skills in a foreign language are intended to be implemented with the support of a teacher. The fact that there are not enough systematic, clear sources for independent use by the student indicates the relevance of the research.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaeva N.A., Toraev B.N., Nurmatova N., Monitoring system for achieving planned results by children in the development of the basic general education program “World of Discoveries”. -T.: Ilm-fan, 2019.
2. Jabborov S.S. Psychological foundations of thinking and speech. – M-T.: Labirint-Ilm-fan, 2019.
3. Jalolov J.J. Methodology of teaching a foreign language: a textbook for students of higher educational institutions (faculties) of foreign languages. – T.: O‘qittu, 2012. – P. 82-83.
4. Lvov, M. R., Ramzaeva, T. G. Methodology of teaching the native language in primary grades. Special textbook for students of pedagogical institutes. “Pedagogy and methodology of primary education”. - Nukus: Education, 2020.
5. Murodov F. K. Diagnostics of the social development of a child: Educational and methodological manual. Navoi-Kazan: LUCH, 2019.
6. Rasulova N.N. The child learns to speak//Vestnik nauki i obrozovaniya, 2022. No. 5.
7. Williams M., Burden R. L. Psychology for language teachers. A social constructivist approach. – L.: Cambridge University Press, 2010. – P. 40.

